

CORRESPONDENCE

Suggestions for fortifying the discoverability of papers published in *European Science Editing*

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European Science Editing (ESE), a platinum open access journal, is gaining recognition as one of the prime outlets for publishing-related topics, as evidenced by its 2019 rise into the second quarter of Scimago's Journal Rankings¹ and by its Scopus CiteScore of 1.3.^{2,3} However, the discoverability of knowledge and information in ESE is currently limited by the fact that manuscripts published before 2003 are not indexed, that none of the papers published before May 2016 have a DOI, and that not all information that appears on the html version of a paper appears on its PDF version, and vice versa.⁴ Finally, because ESE is already indexed in the Directory of Open Access Journals, all papers should be archived on that platform. Such improvements would undoubtedly take time and some resources, but if they could be achieved, the discoverability of the journal would clearly be fortified.⁵

Conflicts of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest relevant to this topic.

Author contributions

The author contributed solely to the intellectual discussion underlying this paper, literature exploration, writing, reviews and editing, and accepts responsibility for the content and interpretation.

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